

SORSE Workshops: FAIR4RS

19 November 2020

Session 2 Breakout Room 2 Notes

Title: What does reusability mean for software?

Lead: Carlos Martinez

Participants: all

Q1: Why do we want to reuse software?

Avoid “reinventing the wheel”. (+1) (+1)

Wasting of funds and time...

Interoperability :-)

Support for existing tools.

Community support

Be reused- get Credit - provide citation notes

Separation of concerns: if a feature in your codebase has already been implemented elsewhere, with a compatible software license and good test coverage, it makes sense to integrate it as an external library. You can then focus on your software, while the feature you outsourced is looked after by experts.

Complexity of research questions and their software requirements forces us to reuse software to allow scientific advances.

Learn from others (by example) and (maybe) be able to extend/adapt it

Reduce wasted effort

Summary: Do not reinvent wheels, avoid duplication of services.

Q2: What are the limitations to achieve this goal?

Platform specific availability (binaries compatible with specific platforms)

Unavailability of code - closed source or restricted "available source"

Code patents

Lack of documentation and examples on how to use a software

Software becomes unmaintained / project is abandoned / project is forked and its community moves to the fork.

As Programming languages advance, software is often rewritten. Other ways of managing legacy software should be promoted.

Not appropriate community support

Users missing skills in software ecosystem handling + software installations -> software projects reimplement instead of introducing external dependencies (which would be better, but need to be installed by the user)

Code doesn't do exactly what you need/want.

Not the most convenient/efficient format to interface with or in

The software you want to re-use might require new dependencies (e.g. libraries not packaged on your operating system, commercial compiler).

Summary: unable to find the code, software is not maintained (software sustainability), lack of required functionality, lack of trust on existing library.

Transcribed comments:

<reuse software>

- Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran: is it possible to distinguish between the motivations or use cases for reuse with the benefits obtained?
- Daniel Garijo: I think this is the question/credit: Why make software reusable?
- Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran: I was considering other aspects, e.g. you reuse because you won't want to re-invent the wheel, and the benefit you may obtain is to have good community support, and the disadvantage is that you may be adding to your technical debt